

INCREASING THE QUANTUM EFFICIENCIES OF ADVANCED PHOTONIC IMAGERS WITH MICROLENS ARRAYS

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ABSTRACT

Single-photon counting detectors or imagers such as front-illuminated single-photon avalanche diodes (SPAD) have a clear benefit in quantum efficiency when augmented with microlenses. Indeed, microlenses can be used to redirect photons initially impinging on the surrounding pixel electronics into the photosensitive surface/volume of the photosensitive device, which dramatically increases the external quantum efficiency – the effective fill-factor. We report the design, deposition, optical characterization, and reliability assessment of such microlenses for demanding applications.

KEYWORDS: Microlenses, microlens array, on-chip lens, imager, SPAD, photon counting

INTRODUCTION

Microlenses, and especially microlens arrays (MLAs), are commonly used as stand-alone optical components, for beam homogenization and shaping, or integrated as wafer-level optics (WLO), either on top of light sources for beam shaping (e.g., on micro-LED or vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser – VCSEL [1]), or on top of light or image sensors as light concentrators. In the latter case, each microlens of the MLA, also known in the photography domain as On-Chip Lens (OCL), redirects the light to the active volume of the pixel located underneath. This increases the external quantum efficiency (EQE) by increasing the pixel effective fill-factor, especially for front-illuminated image sensors and their limited fill-factors.

Nowadays most advanced photonic imagers and photon counters based on single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD) or silicon photon multiplier (SiPM) are front-illuminated. Therefore they can benefit from MLAs to redirect the photons otherwise lost between pixels or bouncing on the metallic interconnects surrounding the photodiode.

CONCEPT

MLAs are commonly integrated directly by the foundries in imaging products for the consumer electronics market e.g. smartphone cameras. However the pixel pitches are therein well below 2 μm [2]. Other companies are producing MLAs, usually with larger pitches and work exclusively on full wafers, for large to very large volumes. Implementing MLAs on those advanced photonic imagers is challenging because their pixel pitches are usually in the tens of μm , because prototypes are manufactured in low volumes or on multi-project wafers, hence delivered as bare dies, and because they often require thin residual layers with high slope angle MLAs.

This work provides a solution compatible with bare dies and was also demonstrated on packaged dies [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Among the various MLA manufacturing methods available [4], this work uses photolithography and thermal reflow to originate the shape of the microlenses (diameter, radius of curvature and inter-lens gap). The obtained so-called microlens master is then used to make a negative mold or stamp which is in turn used multiple times to replicate by UV casting the UV-curable microlens material on the final substrates: wafers or dies [5]–[7]. This process is performed with a mask aligner, allowing alignment between the mold and the photonic imager in the micrometer range or below. The microlens material, which can be an inorganic-organic hybrid polymer [8], is dispensed in liquid state, which allows replicating MLAs on complex topographies as found in front-illuminated imagers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With these MLAs, a SPAD array with a native fill factor of 28% could collect 3 times more light [7] and a SiPM array with a native fill factor of 82.7% could detect 15% more photons at room temperature [9].

These MLAs were previously [3] reported to be stable to temperature variations (100 cycles from -55°C to 125°C passed), exposure to humidity, mechanical shocks and vibrations, as well as irradiation by gamma rays. Microlens materials have here been successfully tested in the 300–2000 nm spectrum range for UV stability, as reported in Figure 1 (up to 15 kJ/cm²).

Reducing the inter-lens gap further improves the benefit brought by MLAs and nearly gapless MLAs are also reported here, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Left: nearly gapless microlens array originated with 23 μm pitch. Right: UV stability test (doses in J/cm^2) of 30 μm thick microlens material deposited on quartz.

CONCLUSIONS

MLAs clearly increase the photon detection efficiency of front-illuminated photonic imagers. Their qualification will continue to assess their proper operation at cryogenic temperatures to address new quantum devices.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Gimkiewicz *et al.*, “Wafer-scale replication and testing of micro-optical components for VCSELs,” presented at the Photonics Europe, Strasbourg, France, Sep. 2004, p. 13. doi: 10.1117/12.544793.
- [2] R. Fontaine, “The State-of-the-Art of Smartphone Imagers,” presented at the International Image Sensor Workshop (IISW), Snowbird, Utah, USA, Jun. 2019, p. R01.
- [3] F. Zanella *et al.*, “Microlens testing on back-illuminated image sensors for space applications,” *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 3636–3644, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1364/AO.383454.
- [4] H. Ottevaere *et al.*, “Comparing glass and plastic refractive microlenses fabricated with different technologies,” *J. Opt. Pure Appl. Opt.*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. S407–S429, Jul. 2006, doi: 10.1088/1464-4258/8/7/S18.
- [5] P. Nussbaum, R. Völkel, H. P. Herzig, M. Eisner, and S. Haselbeck, “Design, fabrication and testing of microlens arrays for sensors and microsystems,” *Pure Appl. Opt. J. Eur. Opt. Soc. Part A*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 617–636, Nov. 1997, doi: 10.1088/0963-9659/6/6/004.
- [6] J. M. Pavia, M. Wolf, and E. Charbon, “Measurement and modeling of microlenses fabricated on single-photon avalanche diode arrays for fill factor recovery,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 4202, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1364/OE.22.004202.
- [7] I. M. Antolovic *et al.*, “Optical-stack optimization for improved SPAD photon detection efficiency,” in *Quantum Sensing and Nano Electronics and Photonics XVI*, Feb. 2019, vol. 10926, pp. 359–365. doi: 10.1117/12.2511301.
- [8] C. Roscher, R. Buestrich, P. Dannberg, O. Rösch, and M. Popall, “New Inorganic-Organic Hybrid Polymers for Integrated Optics,” *MRS Proc.*, vol. 519, p. 239, 1998, doi: 10.1557/PROC-519-239.
- [9] C. Tripl, G. Haefeli, O. Schneider, and E. Zaffaroni, “Microlens-enhanced silicon photomultiplier arrays for LHCb SciFi Tracker Upgrade Ib,” *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. Sect. Accel. Spectrometers Detect. Assoc. Equip.*, vol. 1040, p. 167216, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.nima.2022.167216.

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